

CAUSES OF STRESS AND ITS PSYCHOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article describes stress, which is one of the main problems of people today. At the same time, several solutions are mentioned in the article based on the general information.*

Keywords: *stress, depression, views of G. Selye, cortisol hormone, the power of smile, endorphin hormone, routine, pleasure of life.*

Recently, words like stress and depression and the number of people suffering from them are increasing. This situation sometimes leads to boredom, loss of interest, family disputes and divorces, and most dangerously, suicide. Many people get stressed and depressed and find it very difficult to get rid of it. Because stress is a companion that accompanies almost every person living in life. Persistent depression not only lowers all of your vital signs, it literally burns your body alive. Many people get used to this situation and try to forget the problems caused by it, especially men with alcohol. But this is not the right solution to the problem. Just as a person who is in a good mood and smiling spreads his mood to the people around him, people who are in a bad and depressed mood can't help but show their negative influence on their close relatives and family members and bring them to the same situation. possible The best way to get your life back on track and back to normal is to get rid of stress and depression.

Stress is a state of overexcitement, overexertion, nervousness that occurs as a result of strong influences in humans and animals. A specific neurohormonal reaction developed in the body to various influences. This concept was first introduced into science by G. Selye, who said that stress, along with harming the body, has beneficial aspects as well. Increased stress causes the body to weaken, weaken, and lose the ability to solve problems. Depressed people lose joy in their lives, fall into despair, get stuck in a dead end and cannot get out of it. Life seems black and white to him now, problems seem unsolvable. Again, the hormone of anxiety - cortisol hormone appears in their blood and the blood begins to clot. As a result of this, changes occur in people's inner psyche and physiological conditions: headaches, depression, lack of confidence in the future, negative aspects of life, and negative, dangerous conditions for human life, such as insomnia. Some people do not take any action to get out of the situation and as a result their life goes from bad to worse. Some people find solutions to their problems and turn to psychologists to get their lives back on track and face happy days. Let's look for solutions to relieve stress and depression. To get out of stress and depression, a person should smile for 3 minutes even if he forces himself. A person who smiles and laughs produces endorphins, the hormone of happiness. This hormone dilutes the blood, brings good things to your dreams. They say that a 3-minute artificial smile turns into a natural smile. This smile has a magical power, as a result of which the pain in the human body remains, dilutes the stagnant blood, restores tissues, prevents colds, and also has the property of rejuvenating people. is also important: - people have sorrows that they cannot bring to the surface, they should be brought to the surface without swallowing them; every person has his own shortcomings and mistakes, he should be recognized, accepted and loved as much as possible, only then he will be satisfied with himself and his mood will be

good.- Ba'zi insonlar kasb tanlashda xatolikka yo'l qo'yadi, o'sha kasb bo'yicha ishlash oqibatida unda zo'riqish, charchash, asabiylik holatlari yuzaga keladi, shuning uchun kasb tanlashda adashmaslik, o'zi qiziqadigan kasbida faoliyat yuritishlari lozim.

- One of the most important issues is setting the agenda and following it. Because people don't plan their days, spending a lot of energy on one day leads to not spending it at all on the next day. Being able to distribute energy correctly also relieves stress. Another situation: if you have achieved something, be sincerely happy about it and be proud of yourself.

- Never be alone when you are stressed because it can make you worse. It is very beneficial to be around your family members, friends and loved ones during these times.

- Don't get upset by remembering the sad events of the past. Because bygones are bygones, it's not worth getting upset about. Just live today and plan for tomorrow. Stress and anxiety can also be caused by lack of sleep. To prevent this, regular exercise, taking a hot bath, listening to quiet music, eating right, and deep breathing are also very useful.

At the beginning of the century, the expression "all diseases of the nerves" was changed to "all diseases caused by stress". According to the World Health Organization, 45% of all diseases are related to stress, and some experts believe that this figure is twice as high.

Stress (English: stress - "pressure", "tension", "tension") is a state of extreme excitement and nervousness that occurs in humans and animals as a result of strong influences. Stress is a non-specific reaction of the body under the influence of various extreme factors that threaten to disrupt homeostasis and is characterized by stereotypic changes in the activity of the nervous and endocrine systems. A non-specific neurohormonal reaction that develops in the body to various influences. The term "stress" was defined by the Canadian pathologist G. Selye and introduced into medicine (1936). The scientist called the factor causing stress as stressors, and the changes that occur in the body under their influence as adaptation syndrome. Physical (hot, cold, injury, etc.) and psychological (fear, loud noise, extreme joy) stressors are distinguished. The body develops adaptive biochemical and physiological changes aimed at overcoming the effects of these factors, which depend on the strength of the stressor, the duration of exposure, the physiological system and mental state of the person or animal. In humans and animals with highly developed nervous systems, emotion often acts as a stressor, and it creates the basis for physical stressors. The initial state of the organism is of great importance in the emergence of diseases under the influence of stress. For example, in a patient with hypertension, stress is more severe, that is, with hypertensive crises.

Selye believed that the diseases that develop as a result of stress are either due to the strong influence of the stressor, or the "wrong" reaction of the hormonal system. Because in some cases, distress occurs under the influence of a less strong stressor. Whether stress has a positive or negative effect on the body depends on the body's reaction to this stressor. Measures aimed at actively changing the stress profile increase the body's resistance, and as a result, the disease does not develop, or, on the contrary, if there is no active struggle, the adaptation syndrome weakens and in severe cases can even lead to the death of the organism. The amount of catecholamines in the brain is of great importance in controlling all changes in the body. Thus, the nervous system determines the state of the body's reaction to stress.

Here are some examples of stress relief and relaxation exercises:

1. Close your eyes and lie still for about 2 minutes. Try to imagine the room you are in. First, try to mentally walk the entire room (along the walls), then move along the entire perimeter of the body - from head to heel and back.

2. Pay close attention to your breath, passively realize that you are breathing through your nose. Note that the air you breathe in is slightly cooler than the air you exhale. Focus on your breathing for 1-2 minutes. Trying not to think about anything else.

3. Take a shallow breath and hold your breath for a moment. At the same time, tensing all the muscles for a few seconds, trying to feel the tension in the whole body. Rest while breathing and repeat 3 times.

Each person has a unique ability to cope with stressful situations. Everyone has their own "threshold level" of stress. Criticality reflects the level of importance of safety, stability and predictability of events to a person. The more important a person's sense of security, stability, and predictability, the more painful he or she is to a stressful event. It was also noted that optimistic and cheerful people are psychologically more resilient. A person's personal understanding of the meaning of a stressful event is of great importance. The famous psychiatrist W. Frankl in his works (in particular, in the book "The Man in Search of Meaning") convincingly showed that a person can tolerate anything if he sees the meaning in it. Self-assessment is an assessment of your capabilities. If people evaluate themselves and, accordingly, their abilities sufficiently high, perhaps they will find stressful situations surmountable and therefore less difficult in terms of emotional response. Thus, when faced with stress, people with high self-esteem cope better than those with low self-esteem, which gives them more information about their capabilities and, in turn, improves their self-esteem. helps to increase self-esteem. A person who faces difficult situations adapts to the physical and social environment around him every day. Psychological stress is a concept used to refer to a wide range of emotional states and human actions that occur in response to various extreme effects (stressors). Many factors influence the development of psychological stress, including the characteristics of the stressful event, the interpretation of the event by a person, the influence of a person's past experience, awareness (awareness) of the situation, individual and personal characteristics. of a person. In turn, stress affects human mental processes, particularly higher mental functions.

Different types of stress are classified according to certain criteria. We explain the types of stress according to their usefulness, maintenance and duration.

1. Types of stress based on your sign

1.1. Positive stress

Contrary to popular belief, stress does not always harm the sufferer. This type of stress occurs when a person is under pressure, but subconsciously interprets the situational influence as something that can benefit him.

This stress makes the affected person energetic and full of energy. This stress is associated with positive emotions, such as happiness.

1.2. Anxiety or negative stress

When we are sad, we expect something negative, believing that something will go wrong, which creates anxiety that completely paralyzes us.

Negative stress throws us off balance and depletes the resources available to us in normal situations, resulting in resentment, anger, etc.

2. Types of stress depending on duration

2.1. Acute stress

It's a stress that many people experience, and it's because of the demands we place on ourselves or others. These requirements are related to expectations of the recent past or the near future. In small doses it can be positive, but in high doses it can make us tired, which has serious consequences for our mental and physical health.

Fortunately, this type of stress does not last long, so it is easy to treat and does not leave sequelae. The main symptoms of acute stress:

1. Muscle aches: Headaches, back pain, and contractures are common, among other conditions.

2. Negative emotions: Depression, anxiety, fear, despair, etc.

3. Stomach problems: Stress can cause a huge swing in stomach symptoms; constipation, heartburn, diarrhea, abdominal pain, etc.

4. Overexcitation of the nervous system- Causes symptoms such as increased blood pressure, rapid heart rate, palpitations, nausea, excessive sweating and migraine attacks.

2.2. Acute episodic stress

It is also one of the most commonly treated types of stress in psychological counseling. It appears in people who do not meet their own and society's requirements.

In addition to constant suffering, they are angry and belligerent people because they cannot control all the variables required. Another symptom of people suffering from acute episodic stress is that they constantly worry about the future. With hostility, they are difficult to treat if they are not referred to a specialist and treated.

2.3. Chronic stress

This is the stress that occurs in prisons, wars, or extreme poverty, where you have to be constantly alert. Such stress can also come from childhood trauma. By causing great despair, it can change the range of beliefs and values of the sufferer.

Undoubtedly, this is the most serious stress, with serious and disastrous consequences for the psychological health of the person who is exposed to it. People who suffer daily have mental and physical wear and tear that can last a lifetime. A person can't change a stressful situation, but he can't run away either, he just can't do anything.

A person who has experienced this type of stress often does not know it, because he has suffered for a long time and has become accustomed to it. They may even love it because it's the only thing they know and they don't know or can't do it any other way, so it's common for them to refuse treatment because they feel so good about stress. They believe they are already a part of them.

- There are studies that show the relationship between stress and disease digestive system, cancer, skin diseases and heart problems.

- Security often comes with stress and a feeling of helplessness (they always throw in the towel because they believe, or can't do anything).

- Stress can cause anxiety and depression.

- Suffering from anxiety increases the risk of suicide.

- Risk factors for stress. They are classified according to psychological reasons or environmental reasons. Although, in reality, stress usually arises from both factors combined to a greater or lesser degree.

Psychological or internal remedies

• *Internal and external locus of control: Locus of control refers to the strong belief that what happens to us is controlled by things we do (this is an internal locus of control) or by external causes that the individual cannot change. management). If a person suffers from an external locus of control, they probably experience stress because they believe that there is nothing they can do about a dangerous situation.*

• *Shyness: Some studies show that introverts are more sensitive to stressful situations and tend to be more withdrawn and stressed than more outgoing people.*

• *Self-reflection: If we perceive a situation as threatening, we internalize the same pattern in our thinking. Therefore, under the same conditions, one person can react with peace, and another with stress.*

• *Prone to worry: They are prone to anxiety in the face of uncertainty. Because of this, they are prone to stress.*

Environment or external means

• *Stopping the habit* When something ends, it is difficult to adapt to a new routine (which gives us some stability in our lives), because the psyche spends all its resources to adapt to the new context. For example, ending a vacation.

• *Unexpected events:* Changes in some aspect of our life always make us more or less unstable (even if the change is for the better) and therefore stress us. For example, a new hire.

• *The conflict of conflict:* This is the mental confusion that causes our internal balance to break down, creating chaos in our minds. Re-establishing the order that existed before the chaos requires the use of all the means at one's disposal, thereby causing considerable mental fatigue. For example, get a serious illness.

• *Helplessness before the immovable:* In this context, a person cannot do anything because the situation exceeds the resources available to the person, for example, the death of a relative.

The appearance of stress can cause serious problems in the future, if it is not well dealt with, therefore it is necessary to seek treatment and learn practical means to deal with it. Seeing a clinical psychologist can be the key to learning how to manage stress-related negative emotions and emotions.

Although many methods of combating the effects of stress have been traditionally developed, at the same time, considerable research has been conducted that is inextricably linked with stress prevention and mental stability. A number of self-help approaches based on the theory and practice of cognitive behavioral therapy have been developed to prevent stress and increase stability.

Managing stress has physiological and immune benefits. The following positive results are observed when used together with non-drug intervention:

- treatment of anger or hostility,
- autogenic exercises
- talk therapy (regarding relationship or existential problems)
- biological feedback
- cognitive therapy for anxiety or clinical depression
- stress can be overcome with people and we will get the desired result

Conclusion: In life, a person can get out of any situation. For this, he must have a strong desire. People get so depressed that they get tired of everything, lose interest in anything, and some even lock themselves in a dark room. Today, even young children are experiencing stress and depression. It would not be wrong to say that parents are the reason for this. When a mother cannot prevent stress and depression during pregnancy, and constantly falls into these situations, the child in her body will be born in the same state and will be nervous and depressed. Therefore, it is important for future mothers to prepare themselves for a healthy lifestyle and be free of stress before having a child. The cause of stress and tension in young children is also due to the uneven distribution of mental and physical work. A child who works mentally should rest from time to time. If he follows the above when he is stressed, if he creates a healthy environment in his life, if he keeps himself as far away from depression as possible, if he lives only with pleasure in everything - his life will be beautiful, his body will be healthy both physically and mentally. 'ladi, brings up his children with good morals and achieves family well-being.

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